

CONTINUOUS ADJOINT SHAPE OPTIMIZATION OF INTERNALLY COOLED TURBINE BLADE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an adjoint-based shape optimization framework and its demonstration in a Conjugate Heat Transfer problem in a turbine blading. The gradient of the objective function is computed based on the continuous adjoint method which also includes the adjoint to the turbulence model. The developed software was used to optimize both the blade shape of the internally cooled linear C3X turbine blade and the position of cooling channels aiming at (a) minimum total pressure drop of the hot gas flow and (b) minimum highest temperature within the blade. A free-form parameterization tool, based on volumetric NURBS, controls the blade airfoil contour while the cooling channels are free to move inside the blade, being controlled by the coordinates of their centers. Geometric and flow constraints are included in the performed optimizations keeping the cooling channels away from the airfoil sides and retaining the turbine inlet capacity and flow turning.

KEYWORDS

Internally Cooled Turbine Blades, Conjugate Heat Transfer, Shape Optimization, Continuous Adjoint

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

ABC	Adjoint Boundary Conditions	GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics	NURBS	Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines
CHT	Conjugate Heat Transfer	RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
FAE	Field Adjoint Equation	SD	Sensitivity Derivative
FSI	Fluid-Solid Interface		

Symbols

κ	thermal conductivity	p	static pressure
μ, μ_t	bulk and turbulent viscosities	q_k	heat flux
ρ	density	q_k^{adj}	adjoint heat flux
τ_{km}	stress tensor	R	primal residual vector
τ_{km}^{adj}	adjoint stress tensor	S	domain boundaries
Ψ	vector of adjoint variables	T	temperature
Ω	computational domain	T_a	adjoint temperature
b_i	design variable	v_k	velocity component
F	objective/constraint function	U	vector of conservative variables
h	heat transfer coefficient	V	vector of primitive variables
n_k	unit normal vector component	x_k	Cartesian coordinates

Superscripts/subscripts

F	Fluid	S	Solid
I	Inlet	W	Wall
O	Outlet		

INTRODUCTION

Designing gas turbines with improved performance and longer lifetime for use in aerospace and marine propulsion, land power plants and other industrial applications is of significant importance. Gains are expected from aerodynamically optimized compressors, reduced friction in mechanical parts, optimally performing inlet ducts and nozzles, and/or higher turbine inlet temperatures. The latter is limited by the thermal resistance of the first turbine row blades which nowadays are able to operate at gas temperatures exceeding the limits set by the material thanks to internal and/or external cooling. Thus, the prediction of the interaction of blades and gas flow in gas turbine components is important and this can be done using Conjugate Heat Transfer (CHT) analysis and optimization.

A CHT analysis involves the strongly or loosely coupled solutions of the governing equations in the adjacent fluid and solid domains. In a strongly coupled scheme, PDEs in different domains are solved simultaneously, while in loosely coupled ones, each discipline is solved separately and communicates with the other(s) through their interfaces, Moretti et al. (2017). For the shape optimization of cooled blades, both stochastic and gradient-based methods have been used. The latter rely frequently on the adjoint method to compute the gradient of quantities of interest at a cost independent of the number of design parameters. Gkaragkounis et al. (2018) developed the continuous adjoint method to compute the objective function gradient in CHT shape optimizations for turbulent incompressible flows. There, the shape optimization of an internally cooled 2D turbine cascade and the one of a 3D car engine cylinder cooling system are presented.

The internally cooled C3X turbine blade, reported by Hylton et al. (1983), is a well known test case that has widely been used for validation purposes, Andrei et al. (2014), De Marinis et al. (2015), and is used in this paper as well. For the optimization of the cooling system of the C3X blade, Nowak and Wroblewski (2011) and Mazaher et al. (2016) used evolutionary algorithms and Wang et al. (2015) used the globally convergent method of moving asymptotes.

In this work, the continuous adjoint technique for CHT problems with compressible fluid flows is developed; the adjoint to the turbulence model PDE is also formulated and solved. The optimization targets at minimum total pressure drop of the gas flow and minimum highest blade temperature. The development of the CHT analysis and adjoint-based optimization method was carried out by extending the in-house GPU-accelerated CFD software PUMA (Asouti et al. (2011)).

1 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In a 3D CHT analysis problem, the flow (state) equations in the fluid domain Ω^F are coupled with the heat conduction one in the solid domain Ω^S . In Ω^F , the RANS equations for compressible fluid flows

$$R_n^F = \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{inv}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{vis}}{\partial x_k} = 0 \quad (1)$$

are solved, where $f_k^{inv} = [\rho v_k \quad \rho v_k v_1 + p \delta_{1k} \quad \rho v_k v_2 + p \delta_{2k} \quad \rho v_k v_3 + p \delta_{3k} \quad \rho v_k h_t]^T$ are the inviscid fluxes and $f_k^{vis} = [0 \quad \tau_{1k} \quad \tau_{2k} \quad \tau_{3k} \quad v_\ell \tau_{\ell k} + q_k^F]^T$ the viscous ones. ρ , p and h_t stand for the fluid's density, pressure and total enthalpy, respectively. v_k are the velocity components and δ_{km} the Kronecker symbol. $\tau_{km} = (\mu + \mu_t) \left(\frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_m} + \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_k} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{km} \frac{\partial v_\ell}{\partial x_\ell} \right)$ is the stress tensor. The heat fluxes are $q_k^F = \kappa^F \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_k}$ with $\kappa^F = C_p \left(\frac{\mu}{Pr} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right)$ being the fluid's conductivity. C_p is the specific heat under constant pressure, $Pr=0.72$ and $Pr_t=0.90$. The dynamic viscosity depends on the fluid's temperature T^F , Sutherland (1893). Turbulence is modeled by the one-equation Spalart-Allmaras, Spalart and Allmaras (1994), or the two-equation $k-\omega$ SST, Menter et al. (2003), models. The last state equation, namely the heat conduction equation over Ω^S reads

$$R^S = -\frac{\partial q_k^S}{\partial x_k} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $q_k^S = \kappa^S \frac{\partial T^S}{\partial x_k}$ are the solid's heat fluxes and κ^S is the thermal conductivity of the solid. The flow and heat conduction solvers communicate across the Fluid-Solid Interface (FSI), where $T^F = T^S$ and $q_k^F n_k^F = -q_k^S n_k^S$ must be satisfied. n_k^F, n_k^S are the normal vectors to the FSI pointing towards Ω^F and Ω^S , respectively.

2 CONTINUOUS ADJOINT FORMULATION

This paper deals with two objective functions and two flow constraints. The total pressure drop (F_1) and the highest blade temperature (F_2) are the two objective functions. The inlet capacity (F_3) and hot gas exit flow angle (F_4) are the two flow constraints. These quantities are

$$F_1 = \bar{p}_t^I - \bar{p}_t^O, \quad F_2 = \frac{\sum_{nodes^S} T^S e^{\alpha T^S}}{\sum_{nodes^S} e^{\alpha T^S}}, \quad F_3 = \dot{m}^I \frac{\sqrt{\bar{T}_t^I}}{\bar{p}_t^I}, \quad F_4 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\bar{v}_2^O}{\bar{v}_1^O} \right) \quad (3)$$

where the highest blade temperature is approximated by a differentiable expression where α takes on a large value. $\dot{m}^I, \bar{p}_t^I, \bar{T}_t^I$ are the massflow and the mass-averaged total pressure and total temperature at the hot gas inlet, respectively and $\bar{p}_t^O, \bar{v}_1^O, \bar{v}_2^O$ stand for the mass-averaged total pressure and velocity components at the hot gas exit. Gradient-based optimization algorithms require the gradient of both the objective function and the involved constraints thus, in the remaining of this section, the continuous adjoint formulation for a generic function F (standing for F_1, F_2, F_3 , or F_4) is presented. In continuous adjoint, F is augmented (F_{aug}) by the field integrals of the product of the state equations' residuals and the adjoint variables over Ω^F and Ω^S . For the development of the adjoint method, the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model is considered as an extra state equation. Differentiating F_{aug} with respect to (w.r.t.) the design variables b_i gives

$$\frac{\delta F_{aug}}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\delta F}{\delta b_i} + \int_{\Omega^F} \Psi_n \frac{\delta R_n^F}{\delta b_i} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^F} \Psi^{SA} \frac{\delta R^{SA}}{\delta b_i} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^F} \Psi^D \frac{\delta R^D}{\delta b_i} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^S} T_a \frac{\delta R^S}{\delta b_i} d\Omega \quad (4)$$

where Ψ_n is the n^{th} adjoint flow variable ($n=1, \dots, 5$) and Ψ^{SA} is the adjoint turbulence variable defined in Ω^F . T_a stands for the adjoint temperature at Ω^S . R^D is the residual of the Eikonal equation computing the field of distance from the blade and Ψ^D is the corresponding adjoint variable, Papoutsis-Kiachagias and Giannakoglou (2016). By definition, $\frac{\delta F_{aug}}{\delta b_i}$ and $\frac{\delta F}{\delta b_i}$ are the same. For any function Φ of the state variables (flow variables or T^S), $\frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial b_i} + \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta x_k}{\delta b_i}$ correlates its total and partial derivatives as well as grid sensitivities $\frac{\delta x_k}{\delta b_i}$. Total derivatives of Φ w.r.t. b_i and spatial derivatives permute according to $\frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_\ell} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\ell} \left(\frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta b_i} \right) - \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\ell} \left(\frac{\delta x_k}{\delta b_i} \right)$. After a lengthy mathematical development, $\frac{\delta F_{aug}}{\delta b_i}$ can be expressed as the sum of field (\mathcal{I}_{FAE}) and surface (\mathcal{I}_{ABC}) integrals that include variations in the state variables, and integrals (\mathcal{I}_{SD}) depending on sensitivities of geometrical quantities w.r.t. b_i . The elimination of the multipliers of variations in the state variables gives rise to the field adjoint equations (FAE) along with the adjoint boundary conditions (ABC). Though the adjoint to the turbulence model and the Eikonal equations are solved too, they are omitted in the interest of space. The development of the adjoint Spalart-Allmaras model equation has been published by the same group in Zymaris et al. (2009), though there for incompressible flows. Omitting the turbulence model and Eikonal equations, eq. 4 becomes

$$\frac{\delta F_{aug}}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\delta F}{\delta b_i} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \Psi_n \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial f_{nk}^{inv}}{\partial x_k} \right) d\Omega}_{\mathcal{I}_{inv}^F} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \Psi_n \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial f_{nk}^{vis}}{\partial x_k} \right) d\Omega}_{\mathcal{I}_{vis}^F} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^S} T_a \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial q_k^S}{\partial x_k} \right) d\Omega}_{\mathcal{I}^S} \quad (5)$$

Using the divergence theorem, I_{inv}^F becomes

$$\mathcal{I}_{inv}^F = \underbrace{\int_{S^F} \Psi_n n_k \frac{\delta f_{nk}^{inv}}{\delta b_i} dS}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_b} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} A_{nmk} \frac{\partial \Psi_n}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta U_m}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{FAE}} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \Psi_n \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{inv}}{\partial x_\ell} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}}$$

where $U = [\rho \ \rho v_1 \ \rho v_2 \ \rho v_3 \ \rho E]$ are the conservative flow variables, E is the total energy per unit mass and $A_{nmk} = \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{inv}}{\partial U_m}$ is the inviscid flux Jacobian matrix. An arrow (\rightarrow) underneath any term indicates where this term contributes to (see nomenclature). \mathcal{I}_b gathers all surface integrals. Also,

$$\mathcal{I}_{vis}^F = \underbrace{- \int_{S^F} \Psi_n n_k \frac{\delta f_{nk}^{vis}}{\delta b_i} dS}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_b} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \frac{\partial \Psi_n}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta f_{nk}^{vis}}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\mathcal{I}_{vis,\Omega}^F} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \Psi_n \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{vis}}{\partial x_\ell} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_{vis,\Omega}^F &= \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \frac{\tau_{km}}{\mu + \mu_t} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_{m+1}}{\partial x_k} + v_m \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_k} \right) \frac{\delta(\mu + \mu_t)}{\delta b_i} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^F} \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta k}{\delta b_i} d\Omega - \int_{\Omega^F} \mathcal{K}_k \frac{\delta V_k}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{FAE}} \\ &\quad - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^F} \left(\tau_{km}^{adj} \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_\ell} + q_m^{adj} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\ell} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_m} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}} + \underbrace{\int_{S^F} \left(\tau_{km}^{adj} n_m \frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i} + q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} \right) dS}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_b} \end{aligned}$$

For simplicity, superscript F is omitted from q^{adj} and T in integrals over Ω^F . The same holds for superscript S. Arrays V , \mathcal{K} and the adjoint stresses and heat fluxes are

$$\begin{aligned} V &= [p \ v_1 \ v_2 \ v_3 \ T^F]^T \\ \mathcal{K} &= \left[0 \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{1m}^{adj}}{\partial x_m} - \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_m} \tau_{1m} \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{2m}^{adj}}{\partial x_m} - \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_m} \tau_{2m} \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{3m}^{adj}}{\partial x_m} - \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_m} \tau_{3m} \quad \frac{\partial q_k^{adj,F}}{\partial x_k} \right]^T \\ \tau_{km}^{adj} &= (\mu + \mu_t) \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_{k+1}}{\partial x_m} + \frac{\partial \Psi_{m+1}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{km} \frac{\partial \Psi_{\ell+1}}{\partial x_\ell} + \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_k} v_m + \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_m} v_k - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{km} \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_\ell} v_\ell \right) \\ q_k^{adj,F} &= \kappa^F \frac{\partial \Psi_5}{\partial x_k} \end{aligned}$$

Regarding Ω^S , the integral in eq. 5 takes the form

$$\mathcal{I}^S = \underbrace{- \int_{S^S} T_a n_k \frac{\delta q_k}{\delta b_i} dS}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_b} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^S} \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta q_k}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\mathcal{I}_\Omega^S} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^S} T_a \frac{\partial q_k}{\partial x_\ell} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}}$$

where, by defining $q_k^{adj,S} = \kappa^S \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial x_k}$ as the adjoint heat fluxes in the solid domain,

$$\mathcal{I}_\Omega^S = \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^S} \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta \kappa}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{FAE}} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^S} \frac{\partial q_k^{adj}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_b} + \underbrace{\int_{S^S} q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} dS - \int_{\Omega^S} q_k^{adj} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\ell} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}} \quad (6)$$

Eliminating the multipliers of variations in the state variables in the integrals comprising \mathcal{I}_{FAE} gives rise to the field adjoint equations, which read

$$\begin{aligned} R_m^{adj,F} &= -A_{nmk} \frac{\partial \Psi_n}{\partial x_k} - \mathcal{K}_n \frac{\partial V_n}{\partial U_m} + \mathcal{B}_\mu^F \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial U_m} + \mathcal{B}_c^F \frac{\partial \kappa^F}{\partial U_m} + S_m^{SA} = 0 \\ R^{adj,S} &= -\frac{\partial q_k^{adj,S}}{\partial x_k} + \mathcal{B}_c^S \frac{\partial k^S}{\partial T^S} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial T^S} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{B}_μ^F , \mathcal{B}_c^F , \mathcal{B}_c^S stand for the multipliers of $\frac{\delta\mu}{\delta b_i}$, $\frac{\delta\kappa^F}{\delta b_i}$ and $\frac{\delta\kappa^S}{\delta b_i}$, respectively. S^{SA} are source terms resulting from the differentiation of the turbulence model, Zymaris et al. (2009). $\frac{\delta F}{\delta T^S}$ is the contribution of F to the adjoint heat conduction equation which is non-zero only for F_2 .

Gathering all surface integrals into a single integral per domain gives

$$\mathcal{I}_b = \int_{S^F} \left(\Psi_n n_k \frac{\delta f_{nk}^{inv}}{\delta b_i} - \Psi_n n_k \frac{\delta f_{nk}^{vis}}{\delta b_i} + \tau_{km}^{adj} n_m \frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i} + q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} \right) dS - \int_{S^S} \left(T_a n_k \frac{\delta q_k}{\delta b_i} + q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} \right) dS \quad (8)$$

\mathcal{I}_b splits into surface integrals over (a) inlet/outlet boundaries ($S^{I/O}$) and (b) solid wall boundaries (S^W); the latter include the FSI and adiabatic walls (if any). For the $S^{I/O}$,

$$\mathcal{I}_b^{I/O} = \int_{S^{I/O}} \left[\Psi_n A_{nmk} n_k \frac{\delta U_m}{\delta b_i} + \left(\tau_{km}^{adj} n_m - \Psi_5 \tau_{km} n_m \right) \frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i} + q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} \right] dS$$

where variations in viscous stresses and heat flux are ignored. Eliminating the terms including variations in the flow variables gives rise to the adjoint inlet/outlet conditions, namely

$$\Psi_n A_{nmk} n_k \frac{\partial U_m}{\partial \mathcal{V}_j^{I/O}} + \left(\tau_{km}^{adj} n_m - \Psi_5 \tau_{km} n_m \right) \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial \mathcal{V}_j^{I/O}} + q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\partial T}{\partial \mathcal{V}_j^{I/O}} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \mathcal{V}_j^{I/O}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $\mathcal{V}_j^{I/O}$ denotes any flow quantity extrapolated to $S^{I/O}$ from the interior of Ω^F . For the inlet, \mathcal{V}_j^I stands for the velocity magnitude, and for the outlet, \mathcal{V}_j^O are the outgoing Riemann variables. For the solid walls of Ω^F , taking into account the no-slip condition, eq. 8 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_b^W = & \int_{S^{W,F}} \Psi_{m+1} n_m \frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i} dS - \int_{S^{W,F}} \Psi_{m+1} n_k \frac{\delta \tau_{km}}{\delta b_i} dS - \int_{S^{W,F}} \Psi_5 \frac{\delta (q_k n_k)}{\delta b_i} dS + \int_{S^{W,F}} q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} dS \\ & - \int_{S^{W,S}} T_a \frac{\delta (q_k n_k)}{\delta b_i} dS + \int_{S^{W,S}} q_k^{adj} n_k \frac{\delta T}{\delta b_i} dS + \underbrace{\int_{S^{W,F}} \Psi_5 q_k \frac{\delta n_k}{\delta b_i} dS + \int_{S^{W,S}} T_a q_k \frac{\delta n_k}{\delta b_i} dS}_{\rightarrow \mathcal{I}_{SD}} \end{aligned}$$

The adjoint no-slip condition ($\Psi_2 = \Psi_3 = \Psi_4 = 0$) eliminates surface integrals with variations in the viscous stresses and fluid's pressure. Terms including variations in heat flux and temperature are eliminated by satisfying the adjoint adiabatic and FSI conditions. The former read $q_m^{adj,F/S} n_m^{F/S} = 0$ along the adiabatic walls of Ω^F and Ω^S (if any). The adjoint FSI conditions are $\Psi_5 = T_a$ and $q_k^{adj,F} n_k^F = -q_k^{adj,S} n_k^S$

The remaining field and surface integrals (\mathcal{I}_{SD}) give the SDs of F

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta F}{\delta b_i} = & - \int_{\Omega^F} \left[\Psi_n \left(\frac{\partial f_{nk}^{inv}}{\partial x_\ell} - \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{vis}}{\partial x_\ell} \right) - \tau_{km}^{adj} \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_\ell} - q_k^{adj} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\ell} \right] \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega + \mathcal{I}_{SD}^{SA} \\ & + \int_{\Omega^S} \left(T_a \frac{\partial q_k}{\partial x_\ell} - q_k^{adj} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\ell} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_\ell}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega + \int_{S^{W,F}} \Psi_5 q_k \frac{\delta n_k}{\delta b_i} dS + \int_{S^{W,S}} T_a q_k \frac{\delta n_k}{\delta b_i} dS + \mathcal{I}_{SD}^D \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{I}_{SD}^{SA} , \mathcal{I}_{SD}^D are the contributions of the Spalart-Allmaras and Eikonal equations to the SDs, the expressions of which can be found in Zymaris et al. (2009) and Papoutsis-Kiachagias and Gianakoglou (2016). The grid sensitivities along the parameterized surfaces (here the FSI and the cooling channel boundaries) are computed directly by the differentiation of the parameterization tool. Then, the spring analogy method undertakes their propagation into the domains.

3 THE PUMA SOFTWARE

PUMA is a GPU-accelerated software which involves a RANS equations' solver, a heat conduction equation's solver and their adjoint counterparts along with a set of shape parameterization and grid deformation tools. PUMA runs on a GPU cluster using the shared on-board memory for data transfer between GPUs on the same computational node and the MPI protocol between GPUs on different nodes. Data communications overlap with computations.

The flow and their adjoint equations are discretized on unstructured grids following the vertex-centered finite-volume approach. A multi-stage Runge-Kutta scheme, applied in pseudo-time, with residual smoothing is used to solve the equations. The Roe's upwind scheme and a central scheme with dissipation, both 2^{nd} order accurate, discretize the inviscid fluxes. Residual smoothing employs the first-order accurate Jacobian of the fluid's residuals which is computed in double- though stored in single-precision arithmetic. The so-called mixed-precision arithmetic minimizes GPU memory transactions without jeopardizing solution accuracy. The heat conduction equation is also discretized using vertex-centered finite-volumes and solved using a Krylov-based solver.

The flow and heat conduction solvers are loosely coupled by means of the Aitken's dynamic relaxation formula. Temperature fields computed by the heat conduction solver in Ω^S after performing a sufficient number of internal iterations, are scaled based on the Aitken's formula and imposed as boundary conditions to the flow solver. The flow solver performs a number of pseudo-time steps and the computed heat flux fields on the FSI are communicated back to the heat conduction solver. The flow solver computes heat fluxes along the FSI by integrating the energy equation over the hot gas finite volumes next to the FSI; for instance, for an FSI node i ,

$$(q_m^F n_m^F)_i = \sum_{j \in Neighs(i)} \Phi_{energ}^{inv,ij} - \sum_{j \in Neighs(i)} \Phi_{energ}^{visc,ij}$$

where j are its neighbors and Φ_{energ}^{inv} , Φ_{energ}^{visc} the inviscid and viscous energy fluxes crossing the finite volume interfaces between i and j , respectively. The stability of the coupling scheme is enhanced by computing and communicating the Jacobians of the computed heat fluxes $(q_m^F n_m^F)_i$ w.r.t. T_i^F along the FSI to the heat conduction solver. The heat fluxes along with their Jacobians are computed and communicated at each pseudo-time iteration of the heat conduction solver. The CHT coupled adjoint equations are solved in a similar way.

4 FLOW ANALYSIS OF THE C3X TURBINE

The geometry of the C3X turbine linear cascade can be found in Hylton et al. (1983). The blade is cooled by 10 radial channels. It is made of stainless steel with density $\rho^S = 7900 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and heat capacity $C^S = 586.15 \text{ J/(kg K)}$. Its thermal conductivity is a function of the blade temperature as $\kappa^S = 6.8110 + 0.020716T^S$. Its span is 7.62cm long, with an axial chord of 7.816cm.

According to case 158, for the hot gas, at the inlet, $p_t^I = 243700 \text{ Pa}$, $T_t^I = 808 \text{ K}$ and $Tu^I = 8.3\%$ (turbulence intensity), whereas at the outlet, $p^O = 142530 \text{ Pa}$. For each cooling channel, experimental data for the average temperature and the coolant flow rate are available. The Nusselt number for each channel can be calculated from the empirical expression for turbulent flows in smooth pipes, $Nu_D = 0.022 Cr Pr^{0.5} Re_D^{0.8}$, where the Reynolds number Re_D is determined by the channel's diameter, the measured flow rate and coolant's molecular viscosity. Cr is a correction for a fully developed thermal boundary layer to account for thermal entrance region effects and ranges from 1.03 to 1.12 for the 10 channels, Hylton et al. (1983). The associated heat transfer coefficients are calculated as $h = \kappa Nu_D / D$, where κ is the coolant thermal conductivity and D the channel diameter. The coolant molecular viscosity and thermal conductivity used to calculate the channel's Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficient are based on Sutherland's expression for the measured average T.

A grid of $\sim 312K$ nodes is generated ($\sim 183K$ for Ω^F and $\sim 129K$ for Ω^S). The multi-block structured grid on Ω^F follows a staggered H-O-H grid topology. For Ω^S , the grid has structured

layers close to the pressure and suction sides and the cooling channels to account for the large spatial gradients of T^S in these regions. The rest of Ω^S is filled with triangular elements.

Both the Spalart-Allmaras and $k-\omega$ SST turbulence models are used in the analysis phase. The computed p, T, h distributions on the blade sides are compared with measurements in fig. 1. A good agreement is observed for both models, though the temperature along the suction side (close to the leading edge) is overestimated due to the absence of a transition model.

Figure 1: **Computed (a) pressure, (b) temperature and (c) heat transfer coefficient distributions. Pressure is non-dimensionalized by the inlet total pressure of 243 700 Pa, temperature by 811 K and the heat transfer coefficient by 1135.6 W/m²K.**

5 CHT OPTIMIZATION OF THE C3X TURBINE

In this section, the CHT optimization of the C3X turbine blade is presented. The target was to reduce both the total pressure drop and the highest temperature of the blade while the inlet capacity and the hot gas exit flow angle were constrained to change up to 0.1% from their datum values. A first shape optimization targeted min. total pressure drop under the above flow constraints. The 7×3 volumetric NURBS control grid of fig. 2 was used to control the blade shape. Control points at the leading and trailing edges remained constant while the rest were free to move in the axial and pitchwise directions. To avoid the intersection of the cooling channels with the blade sides, the location of their centers was controlled by the same control grid while their radii were kept constant. In total, 38 design variables were used. To adapt the fluid domain grid to the changing boundaries, the spring analogy technique, Degand and Farhat (2002), was used. The grid inside the blade was generated from scratch based on the new blade shape and cooling channel locations. Fig. 2 also shows the design variable bounds using dashed lines. The method of moving asymptotes, Svanberg (2002), was used and its convergence is plotted in fig. 4 (left). The total pressure drop has decreased by $\sim 21\%$ after 25 cycles by satisfying the flow constraints.

The best solution of the first optimization has almost the same blade's highest temperature with the baseline since this is mainly affected by the location of the cooling channels which only slightly changed by the control box of the first optimization. Thus, the outcome of the first optimization was further optimized for min. highest temperature over the blade aiming at refining the location of the channels. In this second optimization, the blade shape did not change while the cooling channels were free to move leading to 20 design variables (2 per channel). Fig. 3 shows the design variable bounds which were chosen for avoiding channels to overlap with each other. To avoid the cooling channels from overlapping the blade sides, the distance of each cooling channel from the airfoil sides was constrained to be higher than the 30% of their radius. These 20 geometric constraints (2 per channel) ensured the generation of valid grids anew in each optimization cycle and kept the channels away from the blade sides, so as to avoid extremely high $|\nabla T^S|$ (high thermal stresses). After 25 optimization cycles of the second run, the blade's highest T^S has reduced by $\sim 30K$ by still satisfying all geometric constraints. Fig. 4 (right) shows the convergence of the optimization algorithm, where

the blade's temperatures are normalized with T_{ref} . For clarity, only the distance of the 10th cooling channel (the one closer to the leading edge) from the blade's sides is plotted in fig. 4 (right), where distances are normalized with the channels' radii. The best solution of the second optimization has slightly increased (less than 0.1%) total pressure drop compared to the best solution of the first run. This small increase was expected since reducing the highest T^S on the blade results in a higher heat flux from the hot gas to the blade. At the same time, inlet capacity and hot gas exit angle did not differ more than 0.1% from datum values.

Figure 2: **Parameterization of the C3X blade contour for the first optimization.**

Figure 3: **Parameterization of the C3X cooling system for the second optimization.**

Figure 4: **Convergence history of the two optimization runs.**

Fig. 5 presents the Mach number fields computed for the baseline and the optimized configuration (i.e. the outcome of the second optimization run). It is clear that the reduction in total pressure drop was mostly achieved by reducing the flow velocity in the passage throat region.

Fig. 6 presents the computed T^S and $|\nabla T^S|$ fields inside the blade for the baseline and the optimized configuration. In the latter, the first two cooling channels moved towards the leading edge where T^S is high, while the remaining channels moved towards the trailing edge where the highest T^S exists. Thanks to the geometric constraints, the cooling channels did not move too close to the blade sides and the highest $|\nabla T^S|$ changed by less than $\sim 0.3\%$ compared to the baseline. The optimized blade cooling system can be also seen in fig. 7.

CONCLUSIONS

The continuous adjoint method for computing sensitivity derivatives in CHT problems involving turbulent compressible fluid flows was presented. The turbulence model equations were included in the adjoint formulation avoiding the “frozen turbulence” assumption, thus leading to an adjoint model that is consistent, in the continuous sense, to the one used in CHT analyses. This was implemented in the in-house GPU accelerated software PUMA and used to optimize the internally cooled C3X turbine blade. Two optimization runs were performed. The first aimed at reducing the total pressure drop while constraining the turbine inlet capacity and hot gas exit angle, allowing changes up to 0.1% compared to the baseline configuration. The second optimization started with the best solution of the first run aiming at refining the cooling channel locations for minimum highest temperature over the blade.

Figure 5: Computed Mach number fields for the baseline and the optimized configurations.

Figure 6: Computed temperature (left) and temperature gradient magnitude (right) fields for the baseline and the optimized configurations.

Figure 7: Baseline (red) and optimized (blue) blade's shape and cooling system.

The optimized configuration has $\sim 20\%$ less total pressure drop and $\sim 30K$ lower highest blade's temperature. The geometric constraints used in the second run constrained the cooling channels from moving too close to the blade sides increasing the highest temperature gradient magnitude inside the blade less than 0.3% of the baseline. The results show that the developed continuous adjoint CHT method, coupled with gradient-based algorithms, provides a useful tool for the CHT optimization of internally cooled turbine blades.

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